

ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN THE REGIONS

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Experts from international organizations such as the World Bank, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the European Commission, the Eurasian Economic Commission and other world organizations play a major role in studying the problems of transport logistics and forming the relevant information base.

Rapid changes in the transport-logistics market in the conditions of digital globalization require constant study of new trends in development. Some aspects of the formation of the modern international transport-logistics system are revealed in the works of foreign and national authors.

As an important branch of the country's economy and an important factor of the integration of the national economy with the world economy, comprehensive and targeted program measures are being implemented in connection with the rapid qualitative development of the transport and logistics sectors. In this regard, the commissioning of the Khairaton-Mozori Sharif and Angren-Pop railways and the establishment of logistics centers in our country led not only to an increase in domestic transportation, but also to the improvement of Uzbekistan's transit capabilities. In 2017-2021, the Action Strategy on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines important tasks on "Increasing the level of competition among national transport logistics companies". Effective execution of these tasks requires increasing the efficiency of managing the integrated transport-logistics system in our country.

Transport services constitute an important part of the volume of export of services in many national economies. As an example, the Republic of Belarus is a country located at the intersection of transport routes connecting the CIS countries with the European Union and the People's Republic of China, as well as the countries on the Black Sea coast with the Baltic Sea countries. Effective use of the international potential of transport logistics, search for ways to increase the export of transport services is a priority economic task. Consequently, development of economic-mathematical means of forecasting the export of transport services and

identification of the factors significantly affecting it is an important and urgent scientific problem for our country.

Theory issues and the practice of organization of cross-border logistics systems, their functional activities are presented by famous foreign authors DJ Bowersox, LB Mirotina, Yu.M. Nerusha, Yu.I. Rizhikova, VI Sergeeva, T. Vaytina and others. RB in their work focused on some issues of forecasting in the field of transport and logistics. Ivut, AA Surkov, TA Tkalich, AA Frenkel, AV Shurubovich. However, there are still no accurate models for forecasting the export of transport services in the Territories, which are an important element of the country's balance of payments. Econometric forecasting and modeling should fill this gap and provide tools for forecasting the export of freight services in the context of the general and its types (rail, road, pipeline). Forecast values of export of transport services make it possible to determine their contribution to the growth of the country's gross domestic product, identify emerging problems and ways to solve them.

Thus, improving the theoretical foundations of transport logistics, determining its international potential, creating models for forecasting the export of cargo transportation services, and regions are of scientific, theoretical, and practical importance. The relevance of the identified problems, their insufficient development and high socio-economic importance for the regions determine the choice of the goals and structure of the development of this sector.

A new approach to transportation, which today appears as a component of a larger system, covering all aspects of the cargo transportation process, i.e., the flow of information in the shipment, reception, processing, packaging, storage, placement and delivery of cargo. made it possible to conclude that the review is appropriate. Unlike the transport system, which includes a complex of various types of transport related to and cooperating with the implementation of cargo transportation, the integrated transport-logistics system ensures that time and costs are brought to a minimum.

Transport-logistics system means a set of consumers and service providers, as well as users of the management system for them, vehicles, information roads, facilities and other properties. Integrated transport-logistics system is understood as a general management set of combined transport and logistics infrastructures, transport enterprises and vehicles.

As any system consists of certain complex elements that are interconnected and interact, an integrated transport-logistics system also includes a number of complex systems. According to the principles of the systematic approach calculated from the scientific approaches of management, the integrated transport-logistics system can be described as a complex and, in turn, ineffectively managed system. In our opinion, the management of the integrated transport-logistics system is the purposeful regulation of the system by means of economic, organizational-administrative, legal management methods and various levers by the management bodies of the transport company as a management object and subject.

In order to make appropriate management decisions in the effective management of the integrated transport-logistics system, the field should be regularly monitored. As the initial element of the management mechanism lies the management goal. Defining the goal is the most responsible stage in the development and adoption of management decisions, as it determines the strategic and tactical directions of system development. In the dissertation, the mechanism of managing the integrated transport-logistics system is improved based on management concepts, integrated management criteria, and integrated logistics concepts that allow synchronizing logistics operations (Fig. 1). By using this management mechanism, it is possible to effectively organize business processes in the railway network, store cargo, control the movement of goods flows and increase the efficiency of its management, taking into account the continuous operation of the system.

One of the important criteria in evaluating the transport system is logistics indicators. If we look at the logistics efficiency index of the republic, the highest results can be seen in the indicators of infrastructure and on-time delivery. However, compared to the logistics efficiency indicators of foreign countries, they are relatively behind (Table 1). The wide range of logistics services in these countries creates a high cost-effectiveness and is a source of innovative and technological changes and innovations. In 2018, Uzbekistan ranked 99 out of 160 countries according to the logistics efficiency index of countries provided by the World Bank. In our country, the activities of multimodal logistics centers are not sufficiently established, the time taken for export and import operations is extended, and the shortcomings in cargo tracking

and control are the reasons for the decrease of the indicators used to calculate the logistics efficiency index.

The economic efficiency of transport is determined by the share of transport costs in the cost of products produced in the sectors of the country's economy.

The impact of logistics services on the economy is becoming increasingly important. The development of the country's economy leads to the development of the logistics system. On the other hand, as logistics develops, it serves as a basis for the development of other sectors of the economy.

The logistics sector is the backbone of the national economy and is the driving force of all sectors of the agricultural, manufacturing or service industries.

Developing logistics services must be interrelated through the integration of transportation, production, delivery, sales, consumption, service, financing and information.

In-depth study of the demand using the transport balance of the regions, improvement of the quality and reliability of customer service, improvement of the loading-unloading and storage complex, provision of information and forwarding services, strengthening of contractual relations, development of services, various associations, joint-stock companies, leasing companies and the establishment of member enterprises, rolling stock delivery, logistics, marketing, advertising intermediary firms, distribution of container use.

European economist A. Burda expressed the role of logistics services in the economy with the following goals.

Currently, one of the most important issues in the export practice of the country's national economy is logistics services, which are considered by the leaders of the food industry, horticulture, leather industry, textile industry, cotton and other manufacturing enterprises.

In the traditional system, we had to carry a lot of inventory in foreign countries to meet customer satisfaction and provide excellent customer service.

The following proposals and actions are important in the development of transport logistics:

Infrastructure Development: A modern and efficient infrastructure is required for good transport logistics. Development of road networks, railways, airways and rivers, adding new connections and maintaining them are fundamental to providing an efficient transport system.

Learning and applying modern technologies: Integration of modern technologies into transport logistics, automation of road and network systems,

improvement of underground vehicles and introduction of monitoring systems are important in the development of an efficient transport system.

Improving logistics services:Increasing efficiency in the provision of logistics services, delivery and warehousing (Improving storage processes in warehouses, reforming the transport system is important in the development of logistics.

International commercial cooperation:International commercial cooperation is also important in the development of transport logistics. The impact of trade between countries on other sectors, the integration of transport into international systems will help to make changes.

Interactions and collaborations:It is also important to develop mutual relations and cooperation between entities in the field of transport. It is important to study inclusion, consultation and other collaborations instead of multilateral relations between entrepreneurs, government and other organizations.

Personnel training and motivation: The development of transport logistics requires personnel with good training and professional experience. It is very important to organize this process well, motivate and develop personnel, and provide training to learn new technologies.

Political support and guarantees:States should make political decisions and guarantees in the development of transport logistics. Investments, legal protections and other state political measures are important in the development of transport logistics.

Effective Monitoring and Analysis:It is important to build effective monitoring and analysis systems to effectively control transportation system services, improve compliance, and manage bids. These suggestions should be implemented in practice and their results should be analyzed, then necessary changes should be made and development should continue.

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